

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Morakinyo****FIRST NAME: Olumide****PROGRAM CODE: MSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: CRITICAL POINTS OF NOTE

1. When is it not necessary to cite in research writing?

- When the information you are writing about is common knowledge.¹
- When you cannot locate the source of information.
- When you are using a secondary source.
- When the reference date is too old.

2. Which of these is not required in a long quotation?

- Long quotations take not quotation marks.
- They will be indented and look like a separate paragraph.
- They are usually longer than four lines of text.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 10

- They are written in italics.**²
3. **At what point in the writing process do you ensure that your writing addresses your readers' potential questions?**
- Prewriting.
- Writing.
- Revising.**³
- Publishing.
4. **Which of these is not a Form of Writing?**
- Personal writing.
- Subject writing.
- Report writing.
- Proposal writing.**⁴
5. **What can a researcher use to establish the relevance of his reasons in developing a research argument?**
- A warrant.**⁵
- A hypothesis.
- A citation.
- A report.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 7.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Publishing Group, 1999), 7.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 144-259

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 39.

6. Which of these is not an alternative forum for research presentation?

- Oral presentation.
- Poster sessions.
- Group discussions.**⁶
- Conference presentation.

7. How does the Bibliography citation style signal differ from the author-date citation style signal?

- Bibliography style citation uses superscript number at the end of the sentence where the citation appears, while author-date citation style uses a parenthetical citation next to the reference.**⁷
- Bibliography citation style uses only publication dates, while the Author-date citation style uses both author name and publication date.
- Bibliography citation style is used only when referencing a Journal Article; author-date style citation is used for edited books only.
- Bibliography citation style is indicated in all italics while author-date citation style is displayed in all upper case.

8. Which citation management software was the subject of the supplementary study material in Period 4 of the ACA-401?

- JSTOR
- Zotero.**⁸
- Microsoft Word.
- You Tube.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 81.

⁷ Ibid., 87-88.

⁸ Nathanael, Warren, *Managing and Citing Sources Using Zotero.*
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yJiPuoGxvHo&t=16s>

9. **Which author will appear in the reference list when using secondary referencing?**

- The original author whose work is the point of quotation.
- The secondary author that referenced the original work.⁹**
- Both authors appear in the reference list.
- It is not necessary to cite when using secondary referencing.

10. **Which of these is not part of the European Commission's Style Guide Conventions?**

- Diagraphs.
- Input/Output.
- Capital Letters.¹⁰**
- Double Consonants.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 69.

¹⁰ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission, 2011), 5-7.

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